

Fig. 2. (a) Scenario of an optical-band; (b) Topology view at End-to-end SDN controller.

(NBI) plugin has been added specifically for supporting optical connection requests issued by an upper layer End-to-End SDN controller (e.g., an orchestrator of IP and optical layers).

The architecture of the new TeraFlowSDN Optical component is shown in Fig. 1b. The *(Re-)Provisioning Manager* is in charge of managing the optical service request defined by parameters including the source, the destination, and the specifications (e.g., requested information rate of the optical service). Once the (Re-) Provisioning Manager receives a request for an optical service provisioning, the routing, space (e.g., fiber Id considering parallel fibers), band, Operational (OP) mode (i.e., a specific combination of modulation format, symbol rate, and FEC driving a line rate), and spectrum assignment (FLEX-RSA) engine is triggered. Thus, the *FLEX-RSA engine* performs resource allocation for the given request. The FLEX-RSA engine also supports optical-band switching, given the wide spectrum offered by S+C+L or E+S+C+L systems. Fig. 2a shows an example of optical-band scenario, with two OpenConfig terminal-device nodes (T1 and T2) and two multi-granular nodes (R1 and R2). A possible multi-granular node architecture, supporting optical-band switching, has been presented in [9]. In the example, the optical-band over the C-band portion in the range LF-UF (e.g., upper-frequency, lower-frequency) is activated between multi-granular node R1 and multi-granular node R2. Two lightpaths, represented in red lines, exploit the existing optical-band. The lightpaths are independent and can be activated at different times. The FLEX-RSA engine exploits a set of databases: the Traffic Engineering Database (TED), the Physical Layer Database (PL-DB) including physical layer information required to perform quality of transmission (QoT) estimation and consequently required to identify the supported modulation format (thus, the OP mode), and a Label Switched Path Database (LSP-DB) storing information on active optical services.

The overall workflow of the Optical SDN controller (Fig. 1a) runs as follows. A request for an optical service arrives from NBI (1), e.g., from End-To-End SDN controller. The endpoints and the connection specifications (i.e., the bitrate) are taken in charge by the Service component, which triggers the Optical component (2) to run the FLEX-RSA. The Optical component reply includes the FLEX-RSA details (e.g., the portion of the spectrum and operational mode) and the rough configuration parameters for each traversed device (flow entries to be configured). Then, the task scheduler of the TeraFlowSDN's Service component is triggered to invoke the SBI drivers (3), preparing the XML messages to configure the data plane devices via NETCONF protocol, according to the YANG model and the flow entry parameters. The Optical component is also able to perform the RSA and the deployment of traditional wavelength-based optical connections, configuring in the proper way all the traversed optical devices.

3. Experimental demonstration

The experimental setup reflects the overall architecture shown in Fig. 1a and the procedure described in the previous section. The topology presented in Fig.2a is composed of four devices, two transponders and two multi-granular nodes. SBI drivers are connected to the NETCONF SDN agents of the devices. Data plane is emulated through its configuration parameters stored in the NETCONF agents. The OpenConfig YANG data models have been adopted. The standard `openconfig-terminal-device` model has been used for the transponders. The `openconfig-wavelength-router` model has been augmented with a section dedicated to the optical-band parameters for the multi-granular nodes, including the optical bandwidth defined by `lower-frequency` and `upper-frequency` tags, and its association to a fiber (because of the presence of parallel fibers).

During the experiment, an optical connectivity service request from T1 to T2 with a bitrate of 400Gb/s arrives from an upper layer End-to-End SDN Controller connected to the NBI of the Optical SDN controller, and the latter runs the FLEX-RSA algorithm. Since no optical-band among the add/drop multi-granular nodes (e.g., R1 and R2) is available, a new optical-band is instantiated assigning a wide portion of the spectrum among the add/drop multi-granular nodes. Currently, the FLEX-RSA has a priority order: C band, L band and finally S band. Then, the edge optical configuration is performed, including the transponder selection at ingress and egress nodes and a cross-connection (e.g., `openconfig-wavelength-router media-channel`) in the add/drop multi-granular nodes, to exploit the optical-band. Fig. 3a shows the captured NETCONF traffic from TeraFlowSDN to the SDN agents in the data-plane. TeraFlowSDN implements NETCONF over SSH, not allowing to dissect the captured packets in

No.	Time	Source	Destination	Proto	Length	Info
1	0.000000	TFS	agentR1	TCP	754	<pre> (a) Node R1 OB Config Node R2 OB Config Transp. T1 TD Config Node R1 MC Config Node R2 MC Config Transp. T2 TD Config </pre>
27	0.458732	TFS	agentR1	TCP	66	
28	0.547978	TFS	agentR2	TCP	754	
56	0.976179	TFS	agentR2	TCP	66	
57	1.107393	TFS	agentT1	TCP	754	
85	1.604557	TFS	agentR1	TCP	66	
86	1.769814	TFS	agentR1	TCP	754	
112	2.205388	TFS	agentR1	TCP	66	
113	2.293312	TFS	agentR2	TCP	754	
139	2.726243	TFS	agentR2	TCP	66	
140	2.818487	TFS	agentT2	TCP	754	
168	3.249812	TFS	agentT2	TCP	66	

(b)	(c)
<pre> <wavelength-router xmlns="..."> <optical-bands xmlns="http://flex-scale-project.eu/ yang/flex-scale-mg-on"> <optical-band xmlns="..." operation="create"> <index>1</index> <config> <index>1</index> <name>C-BAND</name> <lower-frequency>191560677</lower-frequency> <upper-frequency>195942783</upper-frequency> <admin-status>ENABLED</admin-status> <fiber-parent>3</fiber-parent> </config> </optical-band> </optical-bands> </wavelength-router> </pre>	<pre> <wavelength-router xmlns="..."> <media-channels> <channel xmlns:ns0="..." operation="create"> <index>1</index> <config> <index>1</index> <name>channel1</name> <lower-frequency>191560677</lower-frequency> <upper-frequency>191560677</upper-frequency> <admin-status>ENABLED</admin-status> <optical-band-parent>1</optical-band-parent> </config> <source><config> <port-name>port-1-in</port-name> </config></source> <dest><config> <port-name>port-4-out</port-name> </config></dest> </channel> </media-channels> </wavelength-router> </pre>

Fig. 3. NETCONF messages (a); edit-config message for optical-band (b) and media-channel (c).

Wireshark, so we extracted the messages from the SBI component’s log. The capture starts with the messages sent to configure the optical-band. Messages 1-27 refer to the configuration of multi-granular node *R1*, while messages 28-56 to the configuration of multi-granular node *R2*. In Fig. 3b the details of the XML message sent by the SBI for the optical-band activation are shown. In this case, the portion of the C band comprised between 191.56 THz and 195.94 THz over the fiber with identifier 3 is selected, by configuring the optical-band upper/lower frequency. After the optical-band activation, the lightpath configuration is performed. Then, the messages from TeraFlowSDN towards transponder *T1* (messages 57 – 85), multi-granular node *R1* (messages 86 – 112), multi-granular node *R2* (messages 113 – 139) and transponder *T2* (messages 140 – 168), are reported in the exact order. Fig. 3c shows the resulting XML sent by the SBI of TeraFlowSDN to multi-granular node *R1* for the media-channel configuration from the add port to optical-band interface. The configuration of transponders *T1* and *T2*, not shown due to the lack of space, is performed in the same way, setting the configuration parameters (i.e., frequency, tx-power and operational-mode) resulting from the FLEX-RSA procedure.

The overall control plane delay measured from the request at NBI to the time the agents process the NETCONF messages is around 3.2 s. The contribution related to the FLEX-RSA accounts for 1 – 5ms, with most of the time taken by the NETCONF communication with the devices (around 450 – 500ms for each configuration).

4. Conclusion

This work demonstrates for the first time the TeraFlowSDN Optical component, able to manage optical networks with parallel fibers, space division multiplexing, and optical-band switching. The FLEX-RSA computation contributed 1 – 5ms in the overall optical connection preparation, while the NETCONF communication with the dataplane devices contributed 450 – 500ms for each configuration.

5. Acknowledgement

The authors thank Hussein Zaid and Carsten Schmidt-Langhorst of Fraunhofer HHI for their work on the transceiver agent. This work has been partially supported by the FLEX-SCALE project (G.A. 101096909) under the HORIZON-JU-RIA program, and by the European Union under the Italian National Recovery and Resilience Plan of NextGenerationEU, partnership “Telecommunications of the Future” (PE00000001 - program “RESTART”).

References

1. “ETSI TeraFlowSDN Open-Source Group,” <https://tfs.etsi.org/>, Oct. 2023.
2. R. Vilalta and et al., “Teraflow: Secured autonomic traffic management for a tera of sdn flows,” in *2021 Joint European Conference on Networks and Communications 6G Summit (EuCNC/6G Summit)*, 2021, pp. 377–382.
3. L. Gifre and et al., “Demonstration of zero-touch device and L3-VPN service management using the TeraFlow cloud-native SDN controller,” in *Proc. of OFC*, 2022.
4. P. J. Winzer, “Scaling optical fiber networks: Challenges and solutions,” *Opt. Photon. News*, vol. 26, no. 3, 2015.
5. N. Sambo, A. Ferrari, A. Napoli, N. Costa, J. Pedro, B. Sommerkorn-Krombholz, P. Castoldi, and V. Curri, “Provisioning in multi-band optical networks,” *Journal of Lightwave Technology*, vol. 38, no. 9, pp. 2598–2605, 2020.
6. M. Dallaglio, N. Sambo, F. Cugini, and P. Castoldi, “Control and management of transponders with netconf and yang,” *Journal of Optical Communications and Networking*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. B43–B52, 2017.
7. N. Sambo and et al., “Field trial of sdn-controlled probabilistic constellation shaping supporting multiple rates over a coupled-core multi-core fiber,” *Journal of Lightwave Technology*, vol. 41, no. 12, pp. 3660–3667, 2023.
8. “OpenConfig,” <https://www.openconfig.net/>, Oct. 2023.
9. “FLEX-SCALE Deliverable: D4.1 – Design of a multi-granular SDM/UWB optical switch node,” <https://6g-flexscale.eu/>, Oct. 2023.